

Supplementary material

1. Methods

Skin biopsies

For each patient, two 3-mm punch biopsies were taken from lesional skin and two from non-lesional clinically normal skin. These biopsies were performed in both untreated AD patients (AD-0) and in patients with dupilumab-resistance (Dupi-R). All biopsies were immediately preserved in RNAlater for RNA extraction.

RNA extraction and quantitative reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR)

Total RNA was isolated from the skin biopsies using the TriPure isolation reagent (Roche). Reverse transcription was performed on 1µg of total RNA with oligo(dT) primer (Roche) and Moloney murine leukemia virus reverse transcriptase (Life Technologies). Quantitative PCR amplifications were performed using cDNA from 25ng of total RNA with primer sets and TaqMan probes for human *EF1*, *IFN γ* , *IL4*, *IL5*, *IL6*, *IL9*, *IL13*, *IL17*, *IL19*, *IL20*, *IL22*, *IL22BP*, *IL24*, *IL26*, *filaggrin* and *TNF α* , and qPCR TaqMan MasterMix Taqman (Eurogentec, Liège, Belgium). The sequences of the primers and probes used are listed in Table S2. Samples were first heated for 10 minutes at 95°C. cDNA was amplified as follows: 40 cycles of a two-step PCR protocol for 10 seconds at 95°C and for 1 minute at 60°C. A standard curve with various concentrations of a cloned cDNA fragment was performed for each gene for accurate quantification.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using InStat software (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA). Comparisons between lesional and non-lesional skin within each patient group (AD-0 or Dupi-R) were assessed using Wilcoxon matched pairs tests and comparisons between groups (e.g.,

cytokine induction ratios between AD-0 and Dupi-R) were assessed using Mann-Whitney tests. Correlations were calculated using Spearman correlation coefficients.

Filaggrin sequencing

DNA was extracted from Peripheral blood using the NucleoMag kit (Macherey-Nagel), following the manufactures instructions. Long range PCR primers were designed with primer3 (<https://github.com/primer3-org/primer3>) and synthesized by Integrated DNA Technologies (<http://www.idtdna.com/>). All three *FLG* exons and introns were encompassed by the amplicons. Exon 3 was amplified by a single primer pair that spans the complete exon; additionally, to avoid allelic dropout shorter overlapping primer pairs that split exon3 into two parts were also used. This approach also ensures that LOF variants in the CDS will be present in two independent PCR products. PCR followed the manufacturer's recommended protocol using LongAmp™ Hot Start Taq 2X Master Mix, with 200 ng of DNA as template. PCR products were purified via AMPure Beads (Beckman Coulter).

PCR products from each sample were mixed at equimolar concentration and indexed with the Nanopore ligation native barcoding kit (SQK-NBD112.96 or SQK-NBD114.96) following manufacturer's recommendations. Sequencing was carried out on either 10.4 or 10.4.1 MinION flow cells, basecalling used the Guppy “Super accurate model” and barcodes were required at both ends of the molecule during demultiplexing.

Reads were mapped with minimap2 (<https://github.com/lh3/minimap2>), variants called with clair3 (<https://github.com/HKU-BAL/Clair3>) and LOF variants were annotated with SnpEff (<https://pcingola.github.io/SnpEff/>)

2. Tables

Table S1. Demographics and clinical characteristics of atopic dermatitis patients.

Variable	Dupilumab-resistant AD patients	Treatment-naïve AD patients
Patients, n total	10	9
Median age, in years	36.5	36.0
Sex, male, n	6	6
EASI at inclusion, median (\pm IQR)	16.7 (\pm 6.4)	11.4 (\pm 11.3)
Time to failure of dupilumab, in months (\pm IQR)	11.9 (\pm 15.4)	NA
Atopic comorbidities, n		
Allergic asthma	3	2
Allergic rhinoconjunctivitis	6	7
Previous topical treatments for AD, n		
Emollients	10	9
Topical corticosteroids	10	9
Topical immunomodulators	5	5
Previous systemic treatments for AD, n		
Corticosteroids	4	4
Cyclosporine	7	5
Phototherapy	2	1
Upadacitinib	1	0
Baricitinib	1	0
Others ^a	0	3

Abbreviations: AD, atopic dermatitis; EASI, eczema area and severity index; IQR, interquartile range; NA, not applicable.

^amethotrexate (n=1), azathioprine (n=1), acitretin (n=1)

Table S2. sequence of primers and probes used for quantitative RT-qPCR.

Gene	Forward primer	Reverse primer	Taqman Probe
<i>IFNγ</i>	5'-CTAATTATTCGGTAACTGACTTGA-3'	5'-CGAAACAGCATCTGACTCCTT-3'	5'-TCCAACGCAAAGCAATACATGAACTCATCC-3'
<i>IL4</i>	5'-AGAGCAGAAGACTCTGTGCA-3'	5'-AGCTGCTTGTGCCTGTGGAA-3'	5'-TGCTGCCTCCAAGAACAACACTGAGAAG-3'
<i>IL5</i>	5'-TTGGTGAAAGAGACCTTGGCAC-3'	5'-CTTCAGTGCACAGTTGGTGATTT-3'	
<i>IL6</i>	5'-ACCCCCAGGAGAAGATTCCA-3'	5'-TGTTACATGTCTCCTTTCTCAGG-3'	5'-CCACACAGACAGCCACTCACCTTTCAGAACG-3'
<i>IL9</i>	5'-TGTGACCAGTTGTCTCTGTTGG-3'	5'-GTGGTATTGGTCATCTGAGACAGTCT-3'	5'-TTCCCTCTGACAACACTGCACCAGACCA-3'
<i>IL13</i>	5'-CTGGAATCCCTGATCAACGTG-3'	5'-GGACATGCAAGCTGGAAAAC-3'	
<i>IL17</i>	5'-CCCATCCCCAGTTGATTGGAA-3'	5'-CTCAGCAGCAGTAGCAGTGACA-3'	5'-ACGATGACTCCTGGGAAGACCTC-3'
<i>IL19</i>	5'-TTGGCTCCTGGGTACAATACTG-3'	5'-TCCTTAGCTTGGATGGCTCTTT-3'	5'-TGTCTGATTCCACAGACATGCACCA-3'
<i>IL20</i>	5'-GCCAATTCCTTTCTTACCATCAA-3'	5'-CCCACAATGGCATGTCATGT-3'	5'-AGGACCTCCGGCTCAGTCATGCC-3'
<i>IL22</i>	5'-GCAGGCTTGACAAGTCCAAC-3'	5'-CAGCCAAGCTAGCCTCCTTAG-3'	5'-CCAGCAGCCCTATATCACCAACCGC-3'
<i>IL22BP</i>	5'-CTCAGAATGGAGCATGACGC-3'	5'-CAAAGAGCCATTGACTTGGGT-3'	
<i>IL24</i>	5'-TGCCAAGTGAAGGGGGTTGTTTC-3'	5'-GATGTTATCCTGAGCTTGCATAGTGT-3'	5'-TGGGAAGCCTTCTGGGCTGTGAAA-3'
<i>IL26</i>	5'-ACGCTTTGTGGAGGACTTTCA-3'	5'-CATCTCTCTAGCTGATGAAGCACAG-3'	
<i>FLG</i>	5'-CAGGCTCCTTCAGGCTACATTCTAT-3'	5'-GCAAAGATGTTTTCCAGGAGAGT-3'	
<i>TNFα</i>	5'-CACGCTCTTCTGCCTGCT-3'	5'-GCTTGTCACCTCGGGGTTTC-3'	5'-CCAGGGACCTCTCTTAATCAGCC-3'